

Synthesis, spectral characterization and reactivity study of new Schiff base complexes of divalent manganese, copper and zinc

A. K. De, D. Deb, K. R. Nath Bhowmik and R. N. Dutta Purkayastha*

Department of Chemistry, Tripura University, Suryamaninagar-799 130, West Tripura, India

E-mail : rndp@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 14 May 2008, revised 8 September 2008, accepted 17 September 2008

Abstract : New Schiff base complexes of Mn^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} of the type [M(HL)CH₃COO(H₂O)].2H₂O (M = Mn), [M(HL)CH₃COO(H₂O)] (M = Cu or Zn), H₂L = *N*-(4-carboxyphenyl)salicylaldimine, have been synthesized from the reaction of the Schiff base ligand with the respective metal acetate in a methanolic solution maintaining the metal to ligand ratio as 1 : 1. Complexes have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, FT-IR, NMR, ESR, electronic spectroscopy, room temperature magnetic moment measurements and by TGA/DTA studies. The results of above studies suggest that the newly synthesized complexes are tetra coordinated and Schiff base is acting as bidentate ligand, ligated to the metal center through its phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms respectively. Copper(II) complex appears to be square planar while Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are essentially tetrahedral. Thermal study indicate that Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are thermally stable up to a temperature of ca. 150 °C, whereas manganese(II) complex undergo loss of two molecules of lattice water between 120–125 °C, followed by the loss of coordinated water molecule between 190–200 °C. Mn^{II} complex has demonstrated its catalytic potential in oxidizing the selective organic substrate viz. benzyl alcohol by H₂O₂ as the oxidant.

Keywords : Mn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Schiff base complexes, synthesis, characterization, reactivity.

Introduction

Metal complexes with Schiff base ligand have been subject of intense investigation for the past several years¹. The instant and enduring property of Schiff base ligand undoubtedly stem from the ease with which they can be synthesized, their versatility and also due to their wide ranging complexing ability. The survey of literature reveals that the study of this diverse ligand system is linked with many of the key advances made in inorganic chemistry and has played a seminal role in the development of modern co-ordination chemistry², inorganic biochemistry³, catalysis⁴ and optical materials⁵ etc. A large number of Schiff bases and their metal complexes have been studied because of their interesting and important properties such as their ability to reversibly bind oxygen⁶, and their use in oxygenation and oxidation reaction of organic compounds⁷, redox systems in biological processes⁸, Aldol reactions⁹, in textile industries¹⁰, in radio-pharmaceuticals¹¹, oxidation of DNA¹² and also in host of other important spheres.

Studies involving complexes of 3d transition elements with Schiff base ligand are of current interest not only due to their relevance to biological systems¹³ but also

because many of them exhibit unusual magnetic properties¹⁴, novel structural features¹⁵, antibacterial¹⁶ and catalytic properties¹⁷.

A contemporaneous field of research is concerned with the study of salen and salicylaldimine type of ligand containing redox active metal center such as Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}¹⁸. The work related to design, synthesis and structural characterization of the complexes with salicylaldimine type of ligands have generated much current interest due to their interesting structural features, magnetic, spectral and catalytic properties as well as interesting redox behavior¹⁹. In the present study, we have endeavored to synthesize and characterize the complexes containing tridentate salicylaldimine type of ligand having N,O,O donor sites with redox active metal center viz. Cu^{II}, Mn^{II} and also with a redox non active metal viz. Zn^{II}. An additional goal of the present investigation was also to make an effort to explore the catalytic potential of the newly synthesized complexes towards oxidation of some selective organic substrates.

Experimental

The chemicals used were all reagent grade products.

FT-IR spectra were recorded on KBr pellets in a BOMEM DA-8 FTIR spectrometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO- d_6 solution with a Bruker AMX 400 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

Electronic spectra were recorded in the range 200–900 nm on a Perkin-Elmer model Lambda-25 spectrophotometer, in DMSO solvent. Room temperature magnetic moment measurements were accomplished by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as standard. ESR spectra were recorded in a Bruker EMX, X band spectrometer. The molar conductance of 10^{-3} M solution of the complexes in DMSO were determined by Systronics direct reading conductivity meter number 304. TGA/DTA study was performed by Elmer Pyris Diamond model instrument at a heating rate of 10°C per minute in air in the temperature range of 40–800 $^\circ\text{C}$. Manganese was estimated volumetrically by complexometric titration with EDTA²⁰ using Erio-T as indicator. Copper was estimated iodometrically²¹ and zinc was estimated gravimetrically²² as NH_4ZnPO_4 . Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were estimated by micro analytical methods (Results were obtained from Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Kolkata).

Synthesis :

Synthesis of ligand :

Schiff base ligand (H_2L) was synthesized by slow addition of a methanolic solution of salicylaldehyde 10 cm^3 (1.52 cm^3 , 14.5 mmol) to a methanolic solution of *para*-amino benzoic acid 20 cm^3 (2 g, 14.5 mmol) with continuous stirring, when yellow microcrystalline solid started to separate out. The resultant mixture was refluxed over water bath for *ca.* 30 min. The yellow microcrystalline product thus formed was separated out by filtration, washed with cold ethanol and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl_2 . The product was further recrystallised from ethanol.

Synthesis of Mn^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes :

Schiff base ligand (1.09 g, 4.5 mmol) was dissolved in 20 cm^3 of methanol by heating over water bath. To the resultant clear solution thus obtained, a methanolic solution of the respective metal acetate (1 g, 4.5 mmol) was added with continuous stirring, maintaining ligand : metal ratio as 1 : 1, when solid product started to separate out. The resultant mixture was refluxed over water bath for a further period of *ca.* 30 min. The microcrystalline product so formed was separated by filtration, washed with small portions of ethanol and finally dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Catalytic oxidation of organic substrate with hydrogen peroxide as oxidant :

To a solution of benzyl alcohol (8.80 mmol) in 3 cm^3 of acetonitrile Mn^{II} complex (0.202 mmol) was added and the resultant mixture was stirred for *ca.* 10 min at room temperature. To the reaction mixture 3 cm^3 of H_2O_2 (30%) was then added followed by stirring the whole at *ca.* 50°C for 4 h when original yellow color of reaction mixture gradually changed to reddish brown. The reaction mixture was then concentrated under vacuum and extracted with ether ($3 \times 10\text{ cm}^3$). Etheral layer was washed with water, dried over Na_2SO_4 and then evaporated to dryness. The crude product so obtained was purified by passing the same through a short pad silica-gel column using hexane-ether (1 : 1) mixture as eluent. Evaporation of solvent under reduced pressure afforded the final product. Yield $\sim 53\%$.

A similar reaction was also performed with the substrate without involving the Mn^{II} complex. Even after 12 h of stirring of the reaction mixture at an ambient temperature no significant change in composition of the substrate was observed.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Schiff base ligand (H_2L) can act as a tridentate ligand with N,O,O donor sites and was synthesized by condensation of salicylaldehyde with a methanolic solution of *para*-amino benzoic acid taken in equimolar proportion. Complexes of Mn^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were obtained from a reaction of the Schiff base with the respective metal acetates in a methanolic solution maintaining the ligand to metal stoichiometry as 1 : 1 (Fig. 1). The newly synthesized complexes are colored microcrystalline solids, and stable for a prolong period. Complexes are insoluble in water and are poorly soluble in common organic solvents.

The ligand and complexes were characterized and an assessment of their structure was made on the basis of elemental analyses, FT-IR, electronic, NMR, ESR spectroscopic studies, room temperature magnetic moment measurements as well as by thermogravimetric studies. Elemental analyses data of the compounds indicated that the complexes have metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 1 and agrees well with the proposed formulation of the complexes. Molar conductance measurements of the ligand and complexes in DMSO solution exhibited quite low value ($6\text{--}8\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$) and reveal their non electrolytic nature (analytical and physical data are given in Table 1).

Fig. 1. Reaction schemes for synthesis and reactivity study.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the compounds

Compd./Complex	Colour	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) :				μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
			Found (Calcd.)					
			M	C	N	H		
Ligand (H ₂ L)	Yellow	90	-	69.89 (70.00)	5.98 (5.83)	4.43 (4.16)	-	6.01
[Cu(HL)CH ₃ COO(H ₂ O)]	Green	84	16.71 (16.62)	49.78 (50.65)	3.92 (3.69)	3.46 (3.69)	1.81-1.85	6.77
[Mn(HL)CH ₃ COO(H ₂ O)].2H ₂ O	Yellow-brown	71	14.01 (13.51)	46.98 (47.17)	3.05 (3.43)	4.62 (4.42)	5.84	7.12
[Zn(HL)CH ₃ COO(H ₂ O)]	Yellow	78	16.99 (17.06)	51.02 (50.39)	3.68 (3.67)	4.04 (3.67)	-	6.20

Characterization :

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectra of the ligand and complexes displayed well resolved spectral pattern, significant features of which are summarized in Table 2. The IR spectra showed characteristic differences between the spectral pattern origi-

nating from the complexes and spectra of the free ligand. The notable features of the infrared spectra of the complexes involve absorptions due to coordinated azomethine nitrogen, phenolic oxygen and acetato group. The ligand exhibit characteristic (-C=N) stretching frequency in 1660-1678 cm^{-1} region, while for the complexes (-C=N)

Table 2. Significant IR spectral data of the ligand and complexes (cm^{-1})

Ligand/Complex	$\nu(\text{OH})$	$\nu(\text{COOH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$	$\rho_{\text{r}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	$\rho_{\text{w}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$
Ligand	3050br	1700	1678	1230-1270	-	-	-	-	-	-
[Cu(HL)CH ₃ COO(H ₂ O)]	3412-3380	1700	1618-1622	1298	1594	1367	840	589	521	478
[Mn(HL)CH ₃ COO(H ₂ O)].2H ₂ O	3200-3148	1700	1602	1283	1567	1352	839	622	532	482
[Zn(HL)CH ₃ COO(H ₂ O)]	3412	1700	1608	1287	1582	1351	843	592	527	474

stretching frequency were observed in the region 1618–1622 cm^{-1} . The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ frequency for complexes shifted to a lower value in comparison to free ligand indicating the coordination of imine nitrogen atom of azomethine moiety to the metal center²³. The observance of a medium intensity band in the region 1230–1270 cm^{-1} in the free ligand was attributed to C–O (phenolic) stretching vibration, while for the complexes $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ frequency appeared in the region 1290–1298 cm^{-1} . The C–O stretching frequency is generally shifted to a higher frequency, indicating the formation of bond of oxygen atom of phenolic group with the metal ion²⁴. The deprotonation of phenolic-OH and subsequent coordination of oxygen with metal ion has been further confirmed by reduction in the intensity of the peak in the region 2930–2903 cm^{-1} compared to the corresponding band in the free ligand. The new medium intensity bands in all the complexes in the low frequency region at 521–532 and 478–482 cm^{-1} , which were assignable to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ modes of vibrations, respectively²⁵. Observance of the bands in the low frequency region further manifest the idea of coordination of azomethine nitrogen and deprotonated phenolic oxygen atoms to the metal center.

Appearance of an additional band at *ca.* 1700 cm^{-1} in case of free ligand as well as in compounds is attributable to the free -COOH group²⁶. The unaltered position of this band in the complexes indicate non participation of free carboxylic group (-COOH) of the ligand in coordination. Additional bands for the complexes were observed in the region 1567–1584 cm^{-1} and 1352–1367 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu_{\text{as}}(-\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}-)$ modes of vibrations of the acetato group respectively. The frequency difference between symmetric and antisymmetric stretches $\Delta\nu(\nu_{\text{assym}} - \nu_{\text{sym}})$ *ca.* 210 cm^{-1} is typical of monodentate coordination of acetato group²⁷. The O–H stretching frequency of the ligand is expected in the 3300–3500 cm^{-1} region, however, this frequency is displaced to 3056–3000 cm^{-1} probably due to internal hydrogen bridge between phenolic -OH group and imine nitrogen, OH-----N=C. Occurrence of a broad band at *ca.* 3420 cm^{-1} in the complexes was assigned to $\nu(\text{-OH})$ mode of vibration of water molecule. Although from the appearance and observed position for $\nu(\text{OH})$, no clear inference can be made regarding the nature of the water molecule, however, the consistent appearance of distinct bands at 840 cm^{-1} and 589–602 cm^{-1} due to ρ_{r} and ρ_{w} modes of vibration of water molecule²⁸, provide evidence for the existence of coordinated water molecule in the newly synthesized complexes.

Electronic spectra :

Electronic spectra of copper(II) complex shows distinct bands at *ca.* 300, 410–420 nm, and a shoulder at *ca.* 500 nm respectively. The high intensity band at *ca.* 410–420 nm was assigned to CT transition from filled $d\pi$ orbital of Cu^{II} to the antibonding π^* orbital of the phenolate group. Observance of band at 300 nm attributable to intra ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in case of the ligand was observed at *ca.* 280–285 nm. Appreciable shift of this transition in case of the complex also indicate that the ligand is bonded to the metal center. A weak intensity band at 500 nm (sh) may be attributed to $d-d$ transition, and suggest a probable square planar geometry around Cu^{II} ion in the complex²⁹. In case of the zinc(II) complex, the transitions were observed at *ca.* 300 nm, and at *ca.* 390–400 nm range respectively. The former band was assigned to a charge-transfer (L→M) transition, while the later one was attributed to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of (C=N) group³⁰. Electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complex exhibited three $d-d$ transitions at *ca.* 23809 cm^{-1} (420 nm), *ca.* 26315 cm^{-1} (360 nm) and *ca.* 30303 cm^{-1} (330 nm), which were assigned to ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4E$ (4G state), ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_1$ (4P state), ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4A_2$ (4F state) modes of transitions respectively. A relatively higher intensity transition at 33000 cm^{-1} (300 nm) was attributed to charge transfer transition. The observed spectral band positions suggests the existence of tetrahedral structure for the Mn^{II} complex³¹.

Magnetic moment :

The room temperature (300 K) magnetic moment for copper(II) complex lie between 1.81 to 1.85 B.M., which is typical for square planar to pseudo tetrahedral mononuclear copper(II) complex with $S = 1/2$ spin state and indicate absence of any anti ferromagnetic coupling of spins at that temperature³¹. The magnetic moment value for manganese(II) complex at 300 K was found to be *ca.* 5.84 B.M., close to the spin only magnetic moment ($\mu = 5.92$ B.M.) for five unpaired electrons, corresponding to a $S = 5/2$ spin state. Zinc(II) complex exhibit diamagnetic behavior as expected for a d^{10} system of Zn^{II} ion.

ESR spectrum (Fig. 2) : X-Band ESR spectra of microcrystalline powder of Cu^{II} complex recorded in solid state at 25 °C. The spectra exhibit one band with $g = 2.066$. The shape of the spectrum is consistent with square planar geometry around copper(II) in the complex³².

${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra :

${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra of the ligand and the zinc(II) com-

Fig. 2. Solid state X-band ESR spectra of copper(II) complex.

plex in DMSO- d_6 solution provide information regarding the coordination of the ligand with the metal ion. In NMR spectrum of the ligand singlet due to proton attached to azomethine group (HC=N) was observed at $\delta = 8.9$ ppm (1H, s). In case of the Zn^{II} complex a down field shift of this signal compared to its position in the free ligand is suggestive of the coordination of the Schiff base ligand to the metal center through imine nitrogen. The multiplets due to aromatic protons (8H, m) in case of ligand as well as in the complex were observed in the range 6.8–8 ppm. In the spectra of the ligand signals at $\delta = 10$ ppm (s) and $\delta = 13.7$ ppm (s) were assigned to -OH and -COOH protons respectively. Disappearance of signal due to -OH proton in Zn^{II} complex, is indicative of bonding of phenolic oxygen to the metal ion (C–O–M). The infrared spectrum of the complex also supported this view by exhibiting characteristic absorption due to phe-

Fig. 3. TGA/DTA curve of Cu^{II} complexes.

nolic (C–O) group. There is no other appreciable change in the spectra of the complex, except appearance of a new signal at *ca.* 1.8 ppm which is attributable to -CH₃ proton of acetato group. Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes are paramagnetic in nature, as a consequence of which, their NMR spectra could not be obtained.

Thermal studies :

Thermogravimetric analysis of the complexes were carried out in the temperature range of 40–800 °C in an atmosphere of air. The thermogravimetric analysis data (Table 3) for copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes indicated that after initial dehydration, the compounds undergo gradual decomposition. The thermogram of the two compounds showed that the first stage decomposition occurred between 150–160 °C, corresponding to loss of a molecule of water (observed loss 4.21%, *calcd.* 4.74%). In the next decomposition stage in the temperature range of 310–540 °C, the complexes undergo decomposition in a gradual manner, which may be attributed to the fragmentation and thermal degradation of the organic moiety of the ligand, however, decomposed fragments could not be

Table 3. Thermogravimetric data of complexes

Compd.	Temperature range (°C)	Observed weight loss % (Calcd.)	Final residue (%) (Calcd.)
[M(HL)CH ₃ COO(H ₂ O)] (M = Cu, Zn)	150–160	4.21 (4.74)	
	300–550	Continuous wt. loss	20.67 (20.89)
[Mn(HL)CH ₃ COO(H ₂ O)].2H ₂ O	110–125	8.74 (8.87)	34.15 (34.97)
	190–200	4.65 (4.86)	
	300–800	Continuous wt. loss	

estimated due to continuous weight loss in the process. The residual mass remaining at that stage showed the existence of the respective metal oxides. DTA curve also corroborates the result, by presence of an endothermic peak *ca.* 207 μV at 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The results of thermal study of manganese(II) complex is quite similar to those of the other complexes under discussion, except that the initial decomposition occurring between temperature 110–125 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with the liberation of two molecule of water of crystallization from the complex. The loss of weight at this stage (observed loss 8.74%, *calcd.* 8.87%) is commensurate with the loss of two molecules of lattice water per formula weight of the compound. The intermediate thus formed, undergo further weight loss (observed loss 4.65%, *calcd.* 4.86%) in the temperature range of 190–200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ due to expulsion of another molecule of water. Above 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and up to the final heating temperature of 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the complex undergoes gradual decomposition and the residue thus formed showed the presence of oxo manganese species. Thermal studies thus suggest the presence of coordinated as well as uncoordinated water molecules in the complex. The number of water molecules associated with the complexes need to be characterized carefully as from vibrational spectroscopy alone it is very difficult to distinguish between lattice and coordinated water molecule. Thermal study thus lend support to the idea of existence of both coordinated as well as lattice water in case of manganese(II) complex.

Thus on the basis of chemical analyses in conjunction with FT-IR, electronic spectroscopic study, NMR, ESR, magnetic moment measurements and thermal studies the following probable molecular structure may be proposed for the newly synthesized complexes.

Reactivity study :

To assess catalytic potential of the complexes towards oxidation of selective organic substrates, oxidation reaction were carried out with benzyl alcohol as substrate and H_2O_2 as the oxidizing agent in presence of Mn^{II} complex

in acetonitrile solution (Fig. 1). The major product of catalytic oxidation viz. benzaldehyde was characterized by TLC, and by recording of IR spectra. In the IR spectra of the product absence of any band at *ca.* 3460 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(\text{OH})$, present in case of the substrate, and appearance of a new band at *ca.* 1678 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ were the main changes observed. A similar reaction was also carried out without involvement of the Mn^{II} complex and monitored by TLC at appropriate intervals of time, however, no significant change was observed in the substrate composition even after 12 h of stirring of reaction mixture at ambient temperature. Thus the catalytic potential of Mn^{II} complex in oxidation of selective organic substrate by H_2O_2 has been demonstrated. The result of initial study is encouraging and further studies in this regard are in progress.

Conclusion :

New Schiff base complexes of bivalent manganese, copper and zinc have been prepared and characterized on the basis of spectral, magnetic and thermal studies. On the basis of spectral studies it appeared that complexes are tetra-coordinated, ligated by Schiff base ligand in a bidentate fashion through azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atoms respectively. Coordination polyhedra in the complexes were completed by the presence of an acetate group and a molecule of water respectively. The results of the above studies suggest that copper(II) complex probably posses a square planar structure while those of zinc(II) and manganese(II) are tetrahedral in nature. Exploration of catalytic activity of the synthesized complexes towards oxidation of selective organic substrates was also initiated. Mn^{II} complex exhibited promising catalytic performance towards oxidation of organic substrate viz. benzyl alcohol to benzaldehyde by H_2O_2 as the oxidant.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Head, RSIC, NEHU for IR spectral measurements, Prof. M. Bhattacharjee of IIT, Kharagpur for cooperation in recording of ESR spectra, to Dr. A. Dutta of Kansas University, USA, for NMR spectra, to Dr. S. Hussain of IIT, Guwahati for electronic spectra and magnetic measurements and to Dr. S. Mazumder of the Department of Chemistry, Tripura University for help in carrying out reactivity study. Financial

assistance from UGC (NER), Guwahati is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. S. Yamada, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1999, **192**, 537; D. A. Garnorskii, L. A. Nivorozhkin and I. V. Minkin, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **126**, 1.
2. R. H. Holm, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5632.
3. E. C. Niederhoffer, J. H. Timmons and A. E. Martell, *Chem. Rev.*, 1984, **84**, 137.
4. W. Zhang, J. L. Loebach, S. R. Wilson and E. N. Jacobsen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 2801.
5. J. Tisato, F. Refosco and F. Bandoli, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1994, **135**, 325.
6. S. Park, V. K. Mathur and R. P. Planap, *Polyhedron*, 1998, **17**, 325.
7. A. Nashinaga, H. Ohara, H. Tomita and T. Matsuura, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1983, **24**, 213.
8. L. F. Lindoy (ed.), "The Chemistry of Macrocyclic Ligand Complexes", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1989.
9. K. Maruyama, K. Kubo, Y. Toda, K. Kawasa, T. Mashino and A. Nishinaga, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1995, **36**, 5609.
10. T. Nakamura, K. Niwa, M. Fujiwara and T. Matsushita, *Chem. Lett.*, 1999, 1067.
11. M. A. Green, H. Luo and P. E. Fawick, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 1127.
12. C. J. Burrows, J. G. Muller, G. T. Poulter and S. E. Rokita, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1996, **50**, 337.
13. M. Wang, L. F. Wang, Y. Z. Li, Q. X. Li, Z. D. Xu and D. Q. Qu, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 307; P. Tarasconi, S. Capacehi, G. Pelosi, M. Corina, R. Albertini, A. Bonati, P. P. Dall'Aglio, P. Lunghi and S. Pinelli, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **8**, 154; J. Charo, J. A. Lindencrona, L. M. Carlson, J. Hinkula and R. Kiessling, *J. Virol.*, 2004, **78**, 11321; W. L. Liu, Y. Zou, C. L. Ni, Z. P. Ni, Y. Z. Li, Y. G. Yao and Q. J. Meng, *Polyhedron*, 2004, **23**, 849 and references therein.
14. H. Xu, C. He, Y. Sui, X. M. Pen, L. M. Guo, Y. G. Zhang, S. Nishihara and Y. Hosokoshi, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 4463.
15. I. Mauro, B. Federica, L. Vincenzo, M. Fabio, R. Andrea and B. G. Ucello, *Europ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **9**, 1363.
16. N. N. Gulerman, S. Rollas, H. Erdeniz and M. Kiraj, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2001, **26**, 1.
17. M. R. Maurya and S. Sikarwar, *J. Mol. Catal. (A)*, 2007, **263**, 175; M. Dtagaki and K. Suenobu, *Org. Process. Res. Development*, 2007, **11**, 509; S. Ray, S. F. Mapolie and J. Darkwa, *J. Mol. Catal. (A)*, 2007, **267**, 143; Ana C. D. Midoes, P. E. Aranha, M. P. dos Santos, E. Tozzo, S. Romera, R. H. de A. Santos and E. R. Dockal, *Polyhedron*, 2008, **27**, 59.
18. A. Kilic, E. Tas, B. Deveci and I. Yilmaz, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 4009; J. Kaizer, R. Csonka, G. Barath and G. Speier, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2007, **32**, 1047.
19. V. T. Kasumov, A. Bulut, F. Koksai, M. Aslanoglu, I. Ucar and C. Kazak, *Polyhedron*, 2006, **25**, 1153 and references therein; I. Yilmaz, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2008, **33**, 259; E. Tas, A. Kilic, N. Konak and I. Yilmaz, *Polyhedron*, 2008, **27**, 1024.
20. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longmans, Green and Co., New York, 1962, p. 434.
21. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longmans, Green and Co., New York, 1962, p. 358.
22. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longmans, Green and Co., New York, 1962, p. 532.
23. G. A. Kohawone and K. S. Patel, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1981, 1241; P. Sonsa, J. A. G. Vazquez and A. J. Masaquer, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1984, **9**, 318; A. Mukherjee, M. K. Saha, M. Nethaji and A. R. Chakravarty, *Polyhedron*, 2004, **23**, 2177.
24. R. Srinivasan, I. Sougandi, K. Velavan, R. Venkatesan, B. Verghese and P. S. Rao, *Polyhedron*, 2004, **23**, 1115 and references therein.
25. K. Nakamoto and C. W. Schaipfer, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1972, **6**, 70.
26. J. A. Kieft and K. Nakamoto, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 2561.
27. G. B. Deacon and R. J. Philips, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **33**, 227.
28. I. Nakagawa and T. Schimanouchi, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1964, **20**, 429.
29. S. Chattopadhyay, G. Bocelli, A. Catoni and A. Ghosh, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2006, **359**, 4441.
30. N. A. Nawar, A. H. M. Shallaby, N. M. Hosny and M. M. Mostafa, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2000, **26**, 180.
31. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, New York, 1984, p. 449.
32. A. A. A. Emara, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1999, **29**, 87.